

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-V. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-3(2',4'-diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-*H*/methyl/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

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Several new 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were prepared bearing 2,4-diphenylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine moiety. Their structures were supported by ir and mass spectral study. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

4-Thiazolidinones are associated with various kind of biological activities¹. *s*-Triazine derivatives are also biologically active². With an intention to prepare more active drugs, we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinone derivatives of type 1 by the action of thioglycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acid on Schiff bases obtained by condensing 2,4-diphenylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine with different aromatic aldehydes. The structures were supported by ir and mass spectral studies. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity. Some fragmentations are shown in Scheme 1.

1; R = Aryl, X = H/OH/CH₂COOH

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer, and mass spectra on a Varian MAT-CH₅-DF spectrometer.

2,4-Diphenylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine: 2,4-Diphenylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine³ (0.01 mol) in dioxane was treated with ammonia (0.01 mol) at 80–90° for 1.5 h. The product was isolated and crystallised, (0.8 g, 85%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 63.91; H, 5.96; N, 29.29. C₁₅H₁₇N₆ requires: C, 64.05; H, 6.04; N, 29.89%).

2,4-Diphenylamino-6-benzalamino-*s*-triazine: A mixture of 2,4-diphenylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h at 70–80°. The product was isolated and

crystallised, (1.19 g, 70%), m.p. 195° (Found: C, 72.08; H, 4.79; N, 22.78. C₂₂N₁₃N₆ requires: C, 72.13; H, 4.93; N, 22.96%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) (R = *m*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 450 (OH str.), 3 350 (NH str.), 2 925 (CH str.), 1 590 (C=N str.) and 790 cm⁻¹ (C₈N₈).

Similarly, other aldehydes were prepared (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-*H*/methyl-4-thiazolidinone (1): A mixture of appropriate thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol)/thiolactic acid (0.01 mol) and 2,4-diphenylamino-6-benzalamino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) in benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The contents were then diluted with cold water. The upper organic layer was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water. The product was isolated and crystallised, X = H (1 g, 80%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 65.31; H, 4.35; N, 18.99. C₂₄H₂₀ON₆S requires: C, 65.45; H, 4.55; N, 19.09%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) (R = *m*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 450 (OH str.), 3 350 (NH str.), 2 925 (CH str.), 1 690 (C=O str.), 790 (C₈N₈) and 685 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C str.); *m/e* 44, 51, 65, 77 (base peak), 93, 119, 144, 177, 220, 235 and 354; X = CH₃ (1 g, 80%), m.p. >300° (Found: C, 65.99; H, 4.73; N, 18.37. C₂₅H₂₂ON₆S requires: C, 66.08; H, 4.85; N, 18.5%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) (R = *m*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 460 (OH str.), 3 250 (NH str.), 2 950 (CH str.), 1 690 (C=O str.), 790 (C₈N₈) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C str.).

Similarly, other Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (1): 2,4-Diphenylamino-6-benzalamino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 0.5 h. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Schiff base	X=H		X=OH,		X=OH, COOH			
		M.p. °C	N % : Found/Calcd.	M.p. °C	N % : Found/Calcd.	M.p. °C	N % : Found/Calcd.		
1.	Phenyl	195	22.78 (22.96)	220	18.99 (19.09)	>330	18.37 (18.50)	247d	16.71 (16.87)
2.	Anisyl	190	20.99 (21.21)	199	17.78 (17.87)	300d	17.81 (17.96)	225d	15.79 (15.91)
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	168	21.83 (22.00)	159d	18.31 (18.42)	>330	17.58 (17.87)	>330	16.11 (16.34)
4.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	171	21.95 (22.00)	189d	18.29 (18.42)	>330	17.72 (17.87)	>330	16.18 (16.34)
5.	Salicyl	191	21.98 (22.00)	191	18.28 (18.42)	300	17.69 (17.87)	>330	16.27 (16.34)
6.	Cinnamyl	173	21.32 (21.43)	217	17.98 (18.03)	>330	17.39 (17.50)	188	15.91 (16.23)
7.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	177	20.11 (20.39)	183	17.11 (17.28)	>330	16.69 (16.80)	209	15.20 (15.44)
8.	4-Methoxy-3-hydroxyphenyl	207	20.33 (20.39)	155	17.15 (17.28)	300	16.71 (16.80)	>330	15.23 (15.44)
9.	2-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	188	20.28 (20.39)	217	17.20 (17.28)	>330	16.95 (16.80)	>330	15.28 (15.44)

Scheme 1. Mass spectral analysis of 4-thiazolidinone derivative.

filtered and crystallised (0.8 g, 65%), m.p. 247°d (Found : C, 62.61 ; H, 4.31 ; N, 16.71. $C_{20}H_{22}O_3N_2S$ requires : C, 62.65 ; H, 4.42 ; N, 16.87%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) (R=*o*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 400–2 500 (OH str. bonded), 1 690 (C=O str.), 1 620 (O–C–O str.), 790 (C_8N_8) and 605 cm^{-1} (C–S–C str.).

Similarly, other Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity : 4-Thiazolidinone derivatives were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate⁴ method. The testing was

carried out at a concentration of 50 μg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus* and gram-negative bacteria *Marcasane serratia* and *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger*.

Most of the compounds showed moderate activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi (14–17 mm zone of inhibition). The most active among the Schiff bases are bearing (alongwith zone of inhibition in mm) R=phenyl (17–22), anisyl (18–21), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (17–26), salicyl

(18–25), cinnamyl (18–25), 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl (18–23), 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (17–21) and 2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (18–28). The most active among 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-4-thiazolidinones are bearing R = phenyl (20–23), anisyl (18–23), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (17–24), salicyl (19–21), cinnamyl (18–22) and 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl (18–26).

In case of 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones, maximum activity was shown by the compounds bearing R = *p*-hydroxyphenyl (18–22), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (17–24), 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl (18–22) and 2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (20–21). In case of 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones, maximum activity was shown by compounds bearing R = *p*-hydroxyphenyl (17–21), salicyl (17–21), cinnamyl (23), 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl (17–23), 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (19–20) and 2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (24).

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